

PRODUCT CORDIAL LABELING OF DOUBLE PATH UNION OF C_3 RELATED GRAPHS

Mukund V. Bapat ^{*1}

^{*1}Hindale, Tal: Devgad, Sindhudurg Maharashtra, 416630, India

Abstract:

In this paper we discuss The double path unions obtained on C_3 related graphs for product cordial labeling given by $P_m(2G')$ where $G' = C_3, FL(C_3), C_3^+, \text{bull}, \text{tail}(C_3, 2P_2)$ etc.

Keywords: Labeling; Cordial; Product; Bull Graph; Crown; Flag Graph; Tail Graph; Double Path Union.

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1. Introduction

The graphs we consider are simple, finite, undirected and connected. For terminology and definitions we depend on Graph Theory by Harary [9], A dynamic survey of graph labeling by J.Gallian [8] and Douglas West.[11]. I.Cahit introduced the concept of cordial labeling [5]. There are variety of cordial labeling available in labeling of graphs. Sundaram, Ponraj, and Somasundaram [10] introduced the notion of **product cordial labeling**. A product cordial labeling of a graph G with vertex set V is a function f from V to $\{0,1\}$ such that if each edge uv is assigned the label $f(u)f(v)$, the number of vertices labeled with 0 and the number of vertices labeled with 1 differ by at most 1, and the number of edges labeled with 0 and the number of edges labeled with 1 differ by at most 1. A graph with a product cordial labeling is called a product cordial graph. We use $v_f(0,1) = (a, b)$ to denote the number of vertices with label 1 are a in number and the number of vertices with label 0 are b in number. Similar notion on edges follows for $e_f(0,1) = (x, y)$.

A lot of work is done in this type of labeling so far. One interested in survey may refer Dynamic survey in Graph labeling by J. Gillian. We mention some part of it. Sundaram, Ponraj, and Somasundaram have shown that trees; unicyclic graphs of odd order; triangular snakes; dragons; helms; P_mUP_n ; C_mUP_n ; $P_mUK_{1,n}$; W_mUF_n (F_n is the fan P_n+K_1); $K_{1,m}UK_{1,n}$; $W_mU K_{1,n}$; W_mUP_n ; W_mUC_n ; the total graph of P_n (the total graph of P_n has vertex set $V(P_n) \cup E(P_n)$ with two vertices adjacent whenever they are neighbors in P_n); C_n if and only if n is odd; $C_n^{(t)}$, the one-point union of t copies of C_n , provided t is even or both t and n are even; $K_{2+m}K_1$ if and only if m is odd; C_mUP_n if and only if $m+n$ is odd; $K_{m,n}UP_s$ if $s > mn$; $C_{n+2}UK_{1,n}$; $K_nUK_{n,(n-1)/2}$

when n is odd; $K_n \cup K_{n-1, n/2}$ when n is even; and $P_2 \times n$ if and only if n is odd. They also prove that $K_{m,n}$ ($m, n > 2$), $P_m \times P_n$ ($m, n > 2$) and wheels are not product cordial and if a (p, q) -graph is product cordial graph, then $q \leq (p-1)(p+1)/4 + 1$. In this paper we show that $P_m(2G')$ where $G' = C_3, FL(C_3), C_3^+, \text{bull}, \text{tail}(C_3, 2P_2)$ are product cordial graphs.

2. Preliminaries

2.1. Fusion of Vertex

Let G be a (p, q) graph. Let $u \neq v$ be two vertices of G . We replace them with single vertex w and all edges incident with u and that with v are made incident with w . If a loop is formed is deleted. The new graph has $p-1$ vertices and at least $q-1$ edges. If $u \in G_1$ and $v \in G_2$, where G_1 is (p_1, q_1) and G_2 is (p_2, q_2) graph. Take a new vertex w and all the edges incident to u and v are joined to w and vertices u and v are deleted. The new graph has $p_1 + p_2 - 1$ vertices and $q_1 + q_2$ edges. Sometimes this is referred as u is identified with the concept is well elaborated in John Clark, Holton [6]

2.2. Crown Graph

It is $C_n \circ K_2$. At each vertex of cycle a n edge was attached. We develop the concept further to obtain crown for any graph. Thus crown (G) is a graph $G \circ K_2$. It has a pendent edge attached to each of its vertex. If G is a (p, q) graph then crown (G) has $q+p$ edges and $2p$ vertices.

2.3. Flag of a Graph G denoted by $FL(G)$ is obtained by taking a graph $G = G(p, q)$. At suitable vertex of G attach a pendent edge. It has $p+1$ vertices and $q+1$ edges.

2.4. A bull Graph Bull (G) was initially defined for a C_3 -bull. It has a copy of G with an pendent edge each fused with any two adjacent vertices of G . For G is a (p, q) graph, bull (G) has $p+2$ vertices and $q+2$ edges.

2.5. A Tail Graph (Also called as antenna graph) is obtained by fusing a path p_k to some vertex of G . This is denoted by $\text{tail}(G, P_k)$. If there are t number of tails of equal length say $(k-1)$ then it is denoted by $\text{tail}(G, t p_k)$. If G is a (p, q) graph and a tail P_k is attached to it then $\text{tail}(G, P_k)$ has $p+k-1$ vertices and $q+k-1$ edges.

2.6. Path union of G , i.e. $P_m(G)$ is obtained by taking a path p_m and take m copies of graph G . Then fuse a copy each of G at every vertex of path at given fixed point on G . It has mp vertices and $mq + m-1$ edges. Where G is a (p, q) graph.

2.7. Double path union of G , i.e. $P_m(2G)$ is obtained by taking a path p_m and take $2m$ copies of graph G . Then fuse two copies of G at every vertex of path at given fixed vertex on G . It has $2mp$ vertices and $2mq + m-1$ edges. Where G is a (p, q) graph.

3. Main Results

Theorem 3.1 Double path union of triangles given by $G = P_m(2C_3)$ is product cordial for all m

Proof: We define G as a graph with path P_m given by $(v_1, e_1, v_2, e_2, v_3, e_3, \dots, v_m)$. The one of the copies of C_3 fused at V_i is $(u_{i,1}, e_{i,1}, u_{i,2}, e_{i,2}, u_{i,3}, e_{i,3}, u_{i,1})$. The other copy of C_3 is given by $(w_{i,1}, c_{i,1}, w_{i,2}, c_{i,2}, w_{i,3}, c_{i,3}, w_{i,1})$. Note that $u_{i,1}, v_i, w_{i,1}$ are the same vertices as $v_i; i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. (being common vertex to both copies of C_3 and path vertex v_i).

Define a function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ as follows:

Case $m = 2x$,

$$f(u_{i,j}) = 0, j = 1, 2, 3; i = 1, 2, \dots, x.$$

$$f(w_{i,j}) = 0, j = 1, 2, 3; i = 1, 2, \dots, x.$$

$$f(u_{i,j}) = 1, j = 1, 2, 3; i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x.$$

$$f(w_{i,j}) = 1, j = 1, 2, 3; i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x.$$

The label distribution is $v_f(0,1) = (5x, 5x)$ and $e_f(0,1) = (7x, 7x-1)$.

Case $m = 2x+1$

The f defined as above is followed for $P_{2x}(2C_3)$ part of $P_{2x+1}(2C_3)$ and on the last vertex where $i = 2x+1$ we have,

$$f(u_{i,j}) = 1 \text{ for } i = 2x+1 \text{ and } j = 1, 2, 3.$$

$$f(w_{i,j}) = 0 \text{ for } i = 2x+1 \text{ and } j = 2, 3.$$

The label distribution is $v_f(0,1) = (5x+2, 5x+3)$ and $e_f(0,1) = (7x+3, 7x+3)$.

Thus the graph is product cordial for all m . #.

Theorem 3.2 Let G' be FL (C_3) then $P_m(2G')$ is product cordial. (All structures).

Proof: We define G as a graph with path P_m given by $(v_1, e_1, v_2, e_2, v_3, e_3, \dots, v_m)$. The one of the copies of C_3 fused at V_i is $(u_{i,1}, e_{i,1}, u_{i,2}, e_{i,2}, u_{i,3}, e_{i,3}, u_{i,1})$. The other copy of C_3 is given by $(w_{i,1}, c_{i,1}, w_{i,2}, c_{i,2}, w_{i,3}, c_{i,3}, w_{i,1})$. Note that $u_{i,1}, v_i, w_{i,1}$ are the same vertices as $v_i; i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. (being common vertex to both copies of C_3 and path vertex v_i). The pendent vertices u_i' and w_i' are attached by pendent edges e_i' and e_i'' respectively to vertex $u_{i,2}$ and $w_{i,2}$. Thus G has $7m$ vertices and $9m-1$ edges.

Define a function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ as follows:

Case $m = 2x$,

$$f(u_{i,j}) = 0, j = 1, 2, 3; i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$$

$$f(w_{i,j}) = 0, j = 1, 2, 3; i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$$

$$f(u_i') = 0 \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$$

$$f(w_i') = 0 \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, x$$

$$f(u_{i,j}) = 1, j = 1, 2, 3; i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x.$$

$$f(w_{i,j}) = 1, j = 1, 2, 3; i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x.$$

$$f(u_i') = 1 \text{ for } i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x;$$

$$f(w_i') = 1 \text{ for } i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x.$$

The label distribution is $v_f(0,1) = (8x, 8x)$ and $e_f(0,1) = (9x, 9x-1)$.

Case $m = 2x+1$,

The $P_{2x}(2G')$ part of $P_{2x+1}(2G')$ is labeled first as above.

Figure 3.1: Labeled copy of $P_5(2FL(C_3))v_f(0,1) = (19,20); e_f(0,1) = (22,22);$ Structure 1

for $i = 2x+1$ we have,
 $f(u_{i,j}) = 1$, for all $j = 1, 2, 3$.
 $f(w_{i,j}) = 1$, for all $j = 2, 3$.
 $f(u_i') = 1$;
 $f(w_i') = 0$.

The label distribution is $v_f(0,1) = (8x+3, 8x+4)$ and $e_f(0,1) = (9x+4, 9x+4)$. In above labeling the label of pendent vertex is done separately in the sense that it is independent of which vertex on C_3 the pendent edge is fused with. Hence the same function works for all structures to produce product cordial labeling.

Figure 3.2: Structure 2: path union can be taken at vertex 't'. Any other structure is out of scope

Thus the graph is product cordial for all m . #.

Theorem 3.3 Double path union on bull graph given by $P_m(2bull)$ is product cordial.

Proof: We define G as a graph with path P_m given by $(v_1, e_1, v_2, e_2, v_3, e_3, \dots, v_m)$. The one of the copies of C_3 fused at v_i is $(u_{i,1}, e_{i,1}, u_{i,2}, e_{i,2}, u_{i,3}, e_{i,3}, u_{i,1})$. The other copy of C_3 is given by $(w_{i,1}, c_{i,1}, w_{i,2}, c_{i,2}, w_{i,3}, c_{i,3}, w_{i,1})$. Note that $u_{i,1}, v_i, w_{i,1}$ are the same vertices as $v_i; i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. (being common vertex to both copies of C_3 and path vertex v_i). The pendent vertices are u_i', u_i'' and w_i', w_i'' with corresponding pendent edges $(u_{i,1}u_i'), (u_{i,1}u_i''), (w_{i,1}u_i'), (w_{i,2}u_i'')$ respectively. Thus G has $9m$ vertices and $11m-1$ edges.

Define a function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ as follows:

Case $m = 2x$,

$f(u_{i,j}) = 0, j = 1, 2, 3; i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$
 $f(w_{i,j}) = 0, j = 1, 2, 3; i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$
 $f(u_i^') = 0$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$
 $f(u_i^{''}) = 0$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$
 $f(w_i^') = 0$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$
 $f(w_i^{''}) = 0$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$
 $f(u_{i,j}) = 1, j = 1, 2, 3; i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x.$
 $f(w_{i,j}) = 1, j = 1, 2, 3; i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x.$
 $f(u_i^') = 1$ for $i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x;$
 $f(w_i^') = 1$ for $i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x.$
 $f(u_i^{''}) = 1$ for $i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x;$
 $f(w_i^{''}) = 1$ for $i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x.$
 The label distribution is $v_f(0,1) = (9x,9x)$ and $e_f(0,1) = (11x, 11x-1)$.

The $P_{2x}(2bull)$ part of $P_{2x+1}(2bull)$ is labeled first as above,
 for $i = 2x+1$ we have,
 $f(u_{i,j}) = 1$, for all $j = 1,2, 3.$
 $f(w_{i,j}) = 0$, for all $j = 2, 3.$
 $f(u_i^') = 1;$
 $f(w_i^') = 0.$
 $f(u_i^{''}) = 1;$
 $f(w_i^{''}) = 0.$

Figure 3.3: Pm (2bull), labeled copy, numbers stands for vertex labels

The label distribution is $v_f(0,1) = (9x+4,9x+5)$ and $e_f(0,1) = (11x+5, 11x+5)$.

Thus the graph is product cordial for all m. #.

Theorem 3.4 Double path union on crown C_3^+ given by $G = P_m(2C_3^+)$ is product cordial.

Proof: We define G as a graph with path P_m given by $(v_1, e_1, v_2, e_2, v_3, e_3, \dots, v_m)$. The one of the copies of C_3 fused at v_i is $(u_{i,1}, e_{i,1}, u_{i,2}, e_{i,2}, u_{i,3}, e_{i,3}, u_{i,1})$. The other copy of C_3 is given by $(w_{i,1}, c_{i,1}, w_{i,2}, c_{i,2}, w_{i,3}, c_{i,3}, w_{i,1})$. Note that $u_{i,1}, v_i, w_{i,1}$ are the same vertices as $v_i; i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. (being common vertex to both copies of C_3 and path vertex v_i). At each $u_{i,j}$ a pendent vertex is attached is

$u_{i,j}$, $j = 1, 2, 3$. At each $w_{i,j}$ a pendent vertex is attached is $w_{i,j}'$, $j = 1, 2, 3$. Thus G has $|V(G)| = 11m$ and $|E(G)| = 13m - 1$.

Define a function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ as follows:

Case $m = 2x$,

$$f(u_{i,j}) = 0, j = 1, 2, 3; i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$$

$$f(w_{i,j}) = 0, j = 1, 2, 3; i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$$

$$f(u_{i,j}') = 0 \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, x; j = 1, 2, 3.$$

$$f(w_{i,j}') = 0 \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, x; j = 1, 2, 3.$$

$$f(u_{i,j}) = 1, j = 1, 2, 3; i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x.$$

$$f(w_{i,j}) = 1, j = 1, 2, 3; i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x.$$

$$f(u_{i,j}') = 1 \text{ for } i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x; j = 1, 2, 3.$$

$$f(w_{i,j}') = 1 \text{ for } i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x; j = 1, 2, 3.$$

The label distribution is $vf(0,1) = (11x, 11x)$ and $ef(0,1) = (13x, 13x-1)$.

The P_{2x} (2bull) part of $P_{2x+1}(C_3^+)$ is labeled first as above. For $i = 2x+1$ we have,

$$f(u_{i,j}) = 1, j = 1, 2, 3;$$

$$f(w_{i,j}) = 0, j = 2, 3;$$

$$f(u_{i,j}') = 1 \text{ for } j = 1, 2, 3,$$

$$f(w_{i,j}') = 0 \text{ for } j = 1, 2, 3,$$

The label distribution is $vf(0,1) = (11x+5, 11x+6)$ and $ef(0,1) = (13x+6, 13x+6)$.

Thus the graph is product cordial for all m . #

Theorem 3.4 Double path union on $G' = \text{tail}(C_3, 2P_2)$ given by $P_m(2G')$ is product cordial.

Proof: We define G as a graph with path P_m given by $(v_1, e_1, v_2, e_2, v_3, e_3, \dots, v_m)$. The one of the copies of C_3 fused at v_i is $(u_{i,1}, e_{i,1}, u_{i,2}, e_{i,2}, u_{i,3}, e_{i,3}, u_{i,1})$. The other copy of C_3 is given by $(w_{i,1}, c_{i,1}, w_{i,2}, c_{i,2}, w_{i,3}, c_{i,3}, w_{i,1})$. Note that $u_{i,1}, v_i, w_{i,1}$ are the same vertices as v_i ; $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. (being common vertex to both copies of C_3 and path vertex v_i). At $u_{i,1}$ two pendent vertices are fused $u_{i,1}', u_{i,1}''$ with edges given by $(u_{i,1}u_{i,1}')$ and $(u_{i,1}u_{i,1}'')$. At $w_{i,1}$ two pendent vertices are fused $w_{i,1}', w_{i,1}''$ with edges given by $(w_{i,1}w_{i,1}')$ and $(w_{i,1}w_{i,1}'')$. Thus, G has $|V(G)| = 9m$ and $|E(G)| = 11m - 1$.

Define a function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ as follows:

Case $m = 2x$,

$$f(u_{i,j}) = 0, j = 1, 2, 3; i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$$

$$f(w_{i,j}) = 0, j = 1, 2, 3; i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$$

$$f(u_{i,1}') = 0 \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$$

$$f(w_{i,1}') = 0 \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$$

$$f(u_{i,1}'') = 0 \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$$

$$f(w_{i,1}'') = 0 \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$$

$$f(u_{i,j}) = 1, j = 1, 2, 3; i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x.$$

$$f(w_{i,j}) = 1, j = 1, 2, 3; i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x.$$

$$f(u_{i,j}') = 1 \text{ for } i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x;$$

$$f(w_{i,j}') = 1 \text{ for } i = x+1, x+2, \dots, 2x.$$

$$f(u_{i,1}) = 1 \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$$

$$f(w_{i,1}) = 0 \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, x;$$

The label distribution is $v_f(0,1) = (9x, 9x)$ and $e_f(0,1) = (11x, 11x-1)$.

Case $m = 2x+1$

The $P_{2x}(2G')$ part of $P_{2x+1}(2G')$ is labeled first as above. For $i = 2x+1$ we have,

$$f(u_{i,j}) = 1, j = 1, 2, 3;$$

$$f(w_{i,j}) = 0, j = 2, 3;$$

$$f(u_{i,1'}) = 1,$$

$$f(w_{i,1'}) = 0,$$

$$f(u_{i,1}) = 1,$$

$$f(w_{i,1}) = 0,$$

The label distribution is $v_f(0,1) = (9x+4, 9x+5)$ and $e_f(0,1) = (11x+5, 11x+5)$.

Thus the graph is product cordial for all m . #.

4. Conclusions

We have obtained double path union $G = P_m(2G')$ by fusing two copies of same graph G' at every vertex of a path P_m . We have shown that G is product cordial when G' is 1) triangle C_3 , 2) $Fl(C_3)$, 3) $bull(C_3)$, 4) C_3^+ , 5) $tail(C_3, 2P_2)$. We conjecture that $G = P_m(G')$ is product cordial when G' is 1) cycle C_n , 2) $Fl(C_n)$, 3) $bull(C_n)$, 4) C_n^+ , 5) $tail(C_n, 2P_2)$ etc.

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*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: algeyanpascua@ yahoo.com